

SCOIR Institutional Open Access Policy Report

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Title	SCOIR Institutional Open Access Policy Report			
Description	<p>The SCOIR project is two-year project (2023-2025) funded by the National Open Research Forum (NORF). SCOIR aims to support the goal of 100% open access to publicly-funded research publications by adopting a two-pronged approach to policy and legislative change:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Develop a secondary publishing right for Ireland, drafting legislation in support of secondary publication rights based on an analysis of international and Irish law.2. Develop an open access policy framework for both funders and institutions that is aligned with the National Action Plan for Open Research and international best practice. <p>The project is jointly led by Trinity College Dublin and Technological University Dublin and is supported by a consortium of a wide range of partners and affiliates along with an international advisory board. This document is an outcome of (2) above.</p>			
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Executive Summary

This report describes the creation of the model institutional open access policy fulfilling the SCOIR project's objective of creating an open access policy framework aligned with the Irish policy landscape. The purpose of this report is primarily to document the rationale behind the contents of the policy and explain why decisions were taken, but secondarily to provide this background as guidance for successful approval and implementation of the policy. This report also provides an explanation for why it has not been necessary to include a rights retention component to this policy.

Background

SCOIR stands for Secondary rights, Copyright, Open access, Institutional policies, and Rights retention. This project aims to draft secondary rights legislation for Ireland and by creating an Open Access and Rights Retention policy framework for institutions and funders. The potential impact of secondary rights legislation on institutional rights retention policies has been considered alongside the existing policy landscape and the recommendations of the National Action Plan for Open Research, National Open Research Landscape Report and the Copyright Legislation to Support Rights Retention Policy Brief.¹

This report addresses the project objective of 'Create an open access policy framework aligned with the Irish policy landscape' and describes the output 'Updated, NORF-aligned, institutional OA policy for Irish institutions.' The aim of the project is to create a model policy for Irish research performing organisations (RPOs) which can be adopted in a wide range of local contexts.

This report describes the creation of the model institutional open access policy. The purpose of this report is primarily to document the rationale behind the contents of the policy and explain why decisions were taken, but secondarily to provide this background as guidance for successful approval and implementation of the policy.

Methodology

Timeframe

The institutional open access policy was developed throughout 2024 and early 2025. The policy was drafted between June and October 2024. It was opened to public consultation from 25 October - 15 November 2024 and the draft policy was presented at two events during International Open Access Week on 22 and 23 October 2024. A final version was prepared in January 2025.

Stakeholders

SCOIR's project partners and affiliates represent a broad range of different institutional contexts. The policy was made available for public consultation where comments were received from a range of different stakeholders and domain perspectives including universities not participating in the project and arts and humanities researchers in particular.

Policy review

Existing institutional open access policies were reviewed to understand the degree of commonality across the policy landscape amongst HEIs who already have an open access

¹ <https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.ff36jz222>, <https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.5q485c938>, <https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.jd47gm74p>

policy. From this analysis it became clear that many institutions had not updated their policy for many years and it was not possible to locate a policy for many Irish HEIs. International exemplars were also considered including the latest documentation from the European Commission and examples of rights retention policies from the UK.

Existing frameworks

Two existing open access policy frameworks were used to provide a structure to this model policy: The Canadian Association of Research Libraries' Institutional Open Access Policy Toolkit Version 1.0² and Open-access.network's Open Access Policies.³

Consultation

The policy went through several draft versions with the project partners. Following that the policy was released for open consultation during October/November 2024. Changes were suggested to the work package members and further comments were made. Further changes were also incorporated in light of a revised version of the draft Research Outputs and Open Access legislation, developed by another SCOIR work package. All changes were incorporated into a final draft in January 2025. The iterative versions of the policy are now available via Zenodo.⁴

Policy Sections

Purpose

Following the policy frameworks, a section describing the overarching purpose of the policy was included. Initially this only specified the dissemination argument for open access but following the consultation it was expanded to include preservation of the university's intellectual output. The term university is used throughout the policy as a shorthand, however the policy is applicable to any RPO.

Rationale

The rationale section expands the arguments for the policy being in place and outlines the alignment with institutional strategy as well as national and international policy initiatives. Following the consultation additional initiatives were added and alignment with research assessment initiatives such as the San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment⁵ (DORA) and the Coalition of Advancing Research Assessment⁶ (CoARA) were removed as they are not directly relevant to open research and open access. However it should be noted that this model policy remains in alignment with those initiatives.

² <https://www.carl-abrc.ca/oa-policy-template-and-toolkit/>

³ <https://open-access.network/en/information/policy-frameworks/open-access-policies>

⁴ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15114072>

⁵ <https://sfdora.org/>

⁶ <https://coara.eu/>

Actions required by this policy

This section describes the actions both the institution and individual researchers need to take in implementing the policy. In effect this is the main body of the policy and it describes its requirements.

The first action for the institution is a general one of endorsing the National Action Plan for Open Research⁷. It also encourages researchers in its employment to use open practices and make their work as open as possible. While a general statement, it is important to underline the institution's commitment in this area and the requirements that stem from this, namely, the commitment to achieve 100% open access to research publications by 2030.

The second action for the institution is providing an environment that supports the making of research publications open access; the policy lists some of the ways this can be done, including providing a repository for Green open access, support for Diamond open access publishing and support of read and publish agreements via IReL. During the consultation period, the inclusion of read and publish agreements was flagged by some commentators as being controversial, given that their impact on the transition to open access is uncertain, at this stage. However, read and publish agreements are a method through which many research publications are made open access and they receive a large amount of financial support so they were retained for inclusion. Gold open access is not mentioned specifically because payment for open access outside of read and publish agreements is not generally supported by the institution but may be covered by grant funding or the researcher themselves.

The third, and most important action the institution will take on foot of this policy is providing workflows to ensure that research publications are made openly accessible. This policy is not proposing to impinge on any author or publisher copyright, therefore language articulating the version which can be made available is included. This action also clarifies that the version which the institution makes available will have a Creative Commons license or other open public licence.

An allowance for exceptions and limitations to researchers' obligations was added to the policy following the consultation and in light of updates to the draft Research Outputs and Open Access legislation developed by SCOIR. These are very limited compared with previous versions of open access policies that had a narrower scope and allowed for publisher embargoes. However, they do allow for exceptional situations where publications may not be made open access due to legal reasons such as data protection or national security issues. Postponements, as opposed to embargoes, are allowed in the case of 'overriding public interest'. Examples of overriding public interest include academic freedom and the exceptional nature of a significant and substantial research publication.

To ensure that these postponements are truly treated as exceptions and do not become a frequent practice, the policy states that only a senior officer of the university can decide a postponement. A senior officer would be a vice president or dean of a university.

⁷ National Action Plan for Open Research, 2022, <https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.ff36jz222>

The institution is also required by the policy to monitor compliance with the policy. During the consultation period, the means by which the policy would be monitored was queried by several commenters. As the model policy is a high level document, details of monitoring are not provided within the document but the SCOIR project does intend to provide guidance materials at a later date which will include examples of monitoring compliance with the policy.

In addition to providing an environment and workflows to support open access, the institution is also required to develop its platforms to integrate with the wider landscape – for example, through the use of standardised methods and protocols for inclusion in indexing services such as OpenAIRE. This requirement is not new and was included in the original policy statements on open access from 2012.

There are two actions for researchers. The first is that researchers make their research publications open access as soon as possible after they are accepted for publication and that a version of the publication is deposited in the institutional repository. Both the author's accepted manuscript version *and* the version of record are acceptable for deposit in the repository to allow for publication via gold open access or transformative agreements. The phrase used also does not require the researcher to add a publication to the repository themselves but that the publication must be deposited, allowing for deposit via automated routes where possible. Repository deposit is required to preserve the intellectual output of the institution and reduces reliance on commercial publishers for access to the publications themselves.

The second action for researchers is to include a data availability statement. Feedback suggested that researchers may struggle to provide this, however on review, there are sufficient guidelines available to mitigate this concern. Additionally, many publishers already require data availability statements.

Scope

The policy includes a phrase around to whom the policy should apply. During the creation of the policy, the status of certain categories of staff and students was mentioned. It is recognised that each institution may need to adapt this section to fit their local context and may even have standard language about to whom institutional policies apply.

The policy applies to research publications. Initially the policy's first draft referred to research publications. This was subsequently changed to research outputs to broaden the applicability of this policy to other types of research output including data. The term research output is also used in the Research Outputs and Open Access legislation which has been drafted by work package 2 of this project. During the consultation the term research output raised a number of concerns. In particular if it were to include research data, then the institution would be advocating for deposit of research data in multiple repositories, something which is not generally recommended for research data.

During the drafting of the legislation there was also an active discussion about what constituted a research output, particularly when employees of institutions may also publish

other types of work such as novels, which could provide commercial income. Following the consultation period, it was decided that restricting the policy to research publications made implementation of the policy achievable and also aligns it with the National Action Plan for Open Research. It is also determined by the project that the researcher can determine whether or not a publication is a research publication. Where it is a research publication and will be used for purposes such as research assessment or academic progression, it will be subject to this policy.

Provisos

It is important to clarify that this policy does not impact on researchers ability to choose where they wish to publish their works. Therefore a proviso was included to reflect this. During the consultation period several commenters questioned whether this policy would really allow for this. As a result the decision was made to include an additional phrase about supporting the transition to open access publishing. The other revisions in the policy from the consultation phase, including the provision of a 'postponement' for major works, removes any further obligation from this.

Support services

It is suggested that the institution should include a list of services they offer to support an environment conducive to open access publishing.

Exclusion: Rights Retention

This policy does not include specific language about rights retention. Rights retention is a strategy first popularised by Coalition S which launched a campaign for its adoption in 2020.⁸ The idea of the rights retention strategy is for authors to assert their rights over the author's accepted manuscript version of their publication and make it available in a repository. Coalition S also encourages research institutions to adopt rights retention policies which would require researchers employed by that institution to make their author's accepted manuscript open access via the institutional repository under a Creative Commons license. Rights retention policies have been widely adopted in the UK particularly.⁹

The work of WP2 and its research conducted into a secondary publishing right highlighted that it is not necessary to include such language in an institutional open access policy as publisher copyright does not apply to the author's accepted version of a publication. The policy references the existing relationship researchers have with institutions which are governed by intellectual property policies and this policy does not interfere with that.

This conclusion was reached through the work of another SCOIR work package, developing the draft legislation and it resulted in the effort of another work package, WP3, focused on rights retention being transferred between the policy and legislative work packages.

⁸ <https://www.coalition-s.org/coalition-s-develops-rights-retention-strategy/>

⁹ <https://research.jiscinvolve.org/wp/2024/07/26/institutional-rights-retention-policies-what-next/>

Conclusion

This model institutional open access policy provides a framework that supports the goal of achieving 100% open access to research publications in Ireland. The policy sets out clear institutional commitments, researcher responsibilities, and implementation workflows to support open access. It aligns with the National Action Plan for Open Research and, if enacted, the Research Outputs and Open Access Bill. The policy is intended to be widely adoptable while some institutions may need to adapt the policy to fit their local structure.

The policy is designed to be practical and adaptable, ensuring that institutions can implement it in different local contexts. It focuses on repository deposit, institutional responsibility, and researcher obligations. It does not include a rights retention requirement as the project has determined this is unnecessary in the Irish legal context. Instead, it reinforces existing intellectual property policies and highlights the role of repositories in ensuring open access to research outputs.

Next steps

Creation of guidance materials

The project is working on creating a suite of guidance materials to support institutions implementing the policy and to understand the implications of the draft legislation if it is enacted.

These will include:

- Slide deck
- Briefing notes
- Workflow and procedure documentation
- Monitoring and compliance examples

Dissemination and promotional activities

SCOIR is planning several dissemination activities in 2025 including a series of roadshows in May and June. These will be held across the country to present the project's findings to decision makers within institutions. The project is also planning to create an open educational resource to explain the draft legislation and policy.

Adoption ambitions

The ambition is that this policy will be adoptable by all Irish research performing organisations. While it is acknowledged that some local adaptations will be necessary. It is hoped that those who adopt the policy will retain the key provisions in the policy, i.e. the scope and repository deposit requirements. The table below outlines the SCOIR partner institutions' plans for adopting this policy.

Institution	Plan for policy adoption
Atlantic Technological University	The policy and implementation guide will be raised and recommended for adoption through appropriate channels in ATU, with localisation as required.
Marine Institute	The policy and implementation guide will be raised and recommended for adoption at the Marine Institute, with localisation as required.
RCSI	The OA Policy is being reviewed in 2025 and will seek to incorporate the key provisions from this policy framework.
Trinity College Dublin	Our OA Publications Policy is due for review and we will seek to incorporate the key provisions from this policy framework.
Technological University Dublin	An Open Access to Publications Policy, very closely based on this this model policy, is in the process of being approved by university committees.
University College Cork	UCC hopes to bring this forward for approval very soon, in the next few months - we have engaged with our Director of Research Policy who is eager to move it forward.
University of Limerick	Our Institutional Repository policy is due for renewal and we will seek to incorporate the key provisions from this policy in the revision.
Technological University of the Shannon: Midlands Midwest	TUS's Open Access Policy is currently in draft and is due to be reviewed by the relevant TUS Committee in 2025.
University of Galway	The current policy is being reviewed in February/March. The plan is to use the new policy framework while considering any required localisations. Committee approval is expected in April/June or later.